

High resolution mapping before and after seafloor macrolitter removal by an innovative robotic solution in the Venice lagoon, Italy

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Recent studies indicate that a large percentage of marine litter accumulates on the seafloor. However, the seafloor marine litter is hard to identify and, once found, even harder to remove in an efficient and eco-sustainable way. For this reason, it is crucial to develop new techniques for the mapping and the removal of the seafloor marine litter. Within the EU co-funded H2020 Smart technology for Marine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management (MAELSTROM) project, we carried out repeated multibeam surveys associated with video inspections for ground truthing to map the presence of seabed macro litter in a highly impacted area close to the historical city of Venice, Italy.

In September 2022, an innovative robotic system, i.e. a floating platform combined with an underwater cable-driven robot, was successfully tested for the first time in this area of the Venice lagoon. During this first test, the robotic solution, using a gripping device, removed several macro litter items identified by the high-resolution multibeam system in an efficient and selective way.

In this study, we present how the high-resolution mapping and classification have helped to fine-tune the operations of the innovative robotic system for the marine seafloor litter removal. Finally, we show the first results of the cleaning operations by comparing the data collected before and after the cleaning, useful to evaluate the efficacy of the removal technology.